

SROC III

Third Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

**November, 2-3rd 2024,
Ethno Complex Vrđnickska kula, Vrđnik**

Up-dated GEC-ESTRO recommendations for accelerated partial breast irradiation

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13987841

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In 2009 the GEC-ESTRO published the Patient Selection Criteria for Partial Breast Irradiation (PBI). Since then, other societies have published their recommendations and/or have updated them: ABS in 2013 and 2022 and ASTRO in 2009 and 2017. In the last years, there have been changes in the management of Breast Conservative Treatment. The margins have diminished from 2 mm to no tumor on ink; molecular classification by Her-2 status; Radiotherapy dose de-escalation or even RT omission...

The GEC-ESTRO Breast Group is currently working for updating the old guidelines from 2009 for PBI. The most important changes benefit patients with these criteria: margins, no tumor on ink; age, older than 40 years; DCIS with free margins and no multicentricity; Positive nodes pN1mi; Lobular histology (any histology), any tumour grade, molecular classification (Luminal A, Luminal B, Her-2 positive if they are receiving Her2 directed therapy).

We still do not recommend PBI in case of lymphovascular space invasion, nor in BRCA1/2 mutations, or if the tumor is multifocal/multicentric nor if the patient has received neoadjuvant chemotherapy, nor in Triple Negative tumors.

Keywords: Breast cancer, ESTRO, PBI, Lymphovascular invasion

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2024**

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Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

CIP – Каталогизacija у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (3 ; 2024 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Third Serbian Radiation Oncology
Congress, SROC III, November, 2nd-3rd 2024, Ethno Complex
Vrdnicka Kula, Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. – Novi
Sad : Institut za onkologiju Vojvodine, 2024 (Novi Sad : NS
digiprint). – 60 str. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200. – Str. 3: Introduction / Olivera Ivanov.

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 155485193